

The Use of Movies in Youth Ministry: A Different Approach to the Image-Driven Culture

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this paper is to once again explore the use of movies in a church context youth ministry, with an accent on the diverse benefits which can be achieved. The author will do so by integrating adjacent aspects, relevant to the topic, as: pop culture, image-driven culture, generational research. Finally he argues for a different way of integrating movies as a resource for youth ministry, by using them in the counseling process of ministering to troubled youth.

KEY WORDS: movies, youth ministry, teenagers, pop culture, troubled youth.

In the past decades theologians have manifested an interest in studying the relationship between theology and film¹ or religion and film.² This interest also made its way in youth ministry (our area of interest for this paper), but in a more practical manner. Different youth ministry theoreticians were preoccupied with the use of movies in youth ministry³ (or preaching and teaching ministry in general).⁴ A brief observation made by Barsotti and Johnston seems accurate enough to be worth mentioning here: “Theology is being portrayed in and will be retained from the movies we see each week at the cineplex. Though late to recognize this fact, the church is now awakening to the idea that Hollywood is providing an important

resource for its teaching, preaching, youth ministry, and outreach activities.”⁵ This observation brings forth one of the causes of the use of movies in ministry in general and in youth ministry in particular. The other cause is a cultural one. It seems that at certain points a Christian leader, preacher or youth worker can hardly avoid using movies in ministry at least for the sake of relevancy.

Youth Culture: as Image-Driven

The culture of the Millennials and Post-Millennials⁶ is an image-driven culture⁷ (or media-driven culture)⁸ “where story and metaphor are at the heart of spirituality”⁹—as stated by J. Roberto. And movies always present stories and metaphors that appeal to the public. In this context it is important to bear in mind, as Van Gelder points out, that “movies are a powerful tool for shaping people’s perceptions of reality in our image-driven culture.”¹⁰

This characteristic of today’s culture, image-driven,¹¹ is approached differently by Christians in relation to young people. For the Catholics it seems there is a need and also an opportunity to emphasize the sacraments as means of grace by using their outward signs.¹² For Protestants and also for Evangelicals things seemed to take the form of a challenge, as Todd E. Johnson observes: “Though we are becoming an image-driven culture [the observation was made back in 2002], Protestant Christianity remains image poor in its worship. Protestants have developed a cottage industry of material objects of faith outside the worship context (from fish logos on the back of automobiles to WWJD bracelets for children). Perhaps these are an attempted compensation for the absence of visual images in our worship.”¹³ Probably the reluctance manifested by Protestants and Evangelicals toward images in worship is so powerful that in some parts of the World (for example Romania) is unheard of to use clips or movies in regular worship services (especially in a traditional or conservative Evangelical setting). This is not the case anymore at least during youth meetings. Now, as already stated, a youth worker can hardly avoid using movies

in youth ministry even in a traditional or conservative Romanian Evangelical church.

Movies: tools for youth ministry

Sometimes a talk or a sermon could not be appealing for the adolescents for various reasons. At times the church youth can have the feeling that they are overwhelmed with sermons. It is a good opportunity for the youth leader to take a break from preaching and choose alternative ways to share the message which is needed. An alternative way is watching a movie with the youth group in the youth meeting setting. Probably choosing a blockbuster is not the best idea, because there is a major probability that the youth might have already seen the movie in cinemas. Also, blockbusters tend to be highly entertaining, especially action movies, and lack to offer something more besides that. Often lower budget movies prove to be more instructive than blockbusters. To give just an example: *Bang Bang You're Dead*, released in 2002; a movie about bullying and peer pressure in the high school environment, tells the story of a male teenager who overcomes his anger and bitterness achieved after he experienced bullying as a high school student. Also, slightly older movies can be more inspiring than newer ones, because they show a quite different world than the world Millennials and Post-Millennials live in, though they can still relate to the life situations presented in those movies. For example: *Dead Poets Society*, released in 1989 (but the action is set in 1959); a movie about the complex life of teenagers, including aspects as: friendship, trust and betrayal, inspiring models or mentors, conflict between generations, dreams, love and death.

When using movies in youth ministry—and I argue in favor of watching the entire movie not just the trailer or a selected video¹⁴—is important to prepare in advance. M. Theisen offers important advice on how to prepare:¹⁵ “The key to the success of this strategy is to choose the correct movie. If the young people think the movie is beneath them, they may be bored by it and miss the point. If they think the movie is above them, they may be disappointed and it will lose its impact.”¹⁶ Even more important is to “Select a video

based on the age of the intended audience members and the types of relationships and issues that they would identify with. It should have rich and meaningful relationships, and it should be free of objectionable sex scenes, extreme violence, and constant offensive language that would make it unsuitable to show to a group of young people.”¹⁷ Previewing a movie is very important, because it is the starting point of the preparation. Watch the movie diligently and take notes (focus on characters and their relationships; poignant lines and descriptions of symbolic scenes; find a halfway point that seems to be a natural split of the film and use the halfway point for a break). Review notes and develop sets of information and questions for discussions. It is important to have information and questions to present before the youth group watches the movie. As Theisen suggests: “Develop one or two questions to plant in the young people’s minds before they view the video so that they can be attentive to people and issues you wish to discuss.”¹⁸ Also prepare questions to present at the halfway mark of the movie and questions to present at the end.¹⁹

From personal experience, in general, movies can be a tool in youth ministry in three directions: for the benefit of the youth leader; for the benefit of the relationship between the youth leader and the youth group (at an individual level or at a collective level), and for the benefit of the members of the group (individually or collectively).

1) Watching movies and the benefits of the youth leader

Knowing the specific movies teenagers like (and not just movies, but also music, books, places etc.),²⁰ can help the leader to build closer relationships with them. In this way the movies can become a means of getting to better know the (pop) culture of the teenagers in general, but also the culture of the group in particular.²¹ Often being involved in ministry brings a certain level of isolation. At some point it is going to be difficult to understand the culture of the adolescence. Watching a good movie which presents relevant traces of their ethos could bring important insight for the youth leader and could inform his understanding regarding the struggles, the habits and other aspects of life regarding the church youth. Also

through movies the youth leader can be informed about different problems that teenagers or young people may be facing in different life contexts as: school, family, friends and relationships.²²

I was personally informed in the matter of identifying problems that teenagers can face in school or family environment, problems that need to be addressed at least through counseling, by diligently watching a series that presented all sorts of juvenile social cases: *Judging Amy*, a six season series aired between 1999 and 2005. The series is focused on three major plans: the personal life of a juvenile court judge, Amy Gray (interpreted by Amy Brenneman), who, together with her pre-adolescent daughter, after a divorce still lives with her mother, Maxine Gray (interpreted by Karle Warren), who is a very skilled social worker; then there is the consuming professional life of Judge Gray who is daily confronted with sometimes shocking cases of child neglect and child abuse or juvenile delinquency; and then there is also the not less consuming professional life of Maxine who tries to baldly solve difficult social cases, sometimes over passing the professional barriers.²³

2) Watching movies and the benefits in the relationship between the youth leader and the youth group

Movies can be a tool used to involve the teenagers in the personal life of the youth leader. By taking some of them along with his family to the movies, for example, the youth leader can find this quite helpful in developing stronger relationships with the youth, but also trust and genuineness.²⁴ This approach can also be a tool in discipleship and mentoring the future leaders of the youth group. The youth leader can also be taught by movies on how to approach the younger generation in order to gain trust and develop a more efficient youth ministry.

A classic movie which I recommend for every youth leader, regarding the importance of relationship between the leader and the group in terms of trust and genuineness, is *Sleepers* (starring Jason Patric, Brad Pitt, Robert De Niro, Dustin Hoffman, Vittorio Gassmann and Kevin Bacon), released in 1996 and based on *New York Times* bestselling Lorenzo Carcaterra's 1995 novel of the same

name;²⁵ an American legal crime drama movie which tells the story of four childhood friends that face the consequences of a gone wrong prank, being sentenced to detention in a state facility for boys. The abuse suffered during the detention period changed their lives and friendship forever. After 14 years the friends have the chance to take revenge on the guards that systematically abused them. For the final strike, in court, they need the help of Father Robert Carillo, a local priest in the neighborhood in which the friends grew up in, who remained a father figure to the boys. The priest is ready to bend his principles and is willing to give false testimony in court so that the boys can have their vengeance.

3) Watching movies and the benefits of the members of the group

Faith or moral topics can easily be taught by using movies. Movies can be “a starting point for a discussion about Christian values that may or may not be present in the movies.”²⁶ The advice of C. J. Semmel is to: “Take advantage of youth’s interest in movies to provide them with a few observations and reflections on the themes of current popular movies.”²⁷ It could be said that, in a sense, movies can substitute a lesson or a sermon, if the message of the movie is clear enough and if the movie itself appeals to the youth.

Watching a movie together as a group is quite different from watching it individually, because the adolescents can relate together to the same story, as homogenous group. Watching a movie at home is a highly individualistic and subjective activity. So are the conclusions which one draws after watching it alone. But watching a movie together with other friends can help relate to the multiple stories which are told in the movie and relate to those different stories which other members of the group identified with.

To give an example from *Bang Bang You’re Dead*. After watching the movie alone the adolescent who others make fun of or who is bullied at school can easily identify himself with the main character of the story, Trevor Adams (interpreted by Ben Foster), who from the best student of the school becomes the black sheep of the school after he was trashed by the football team in the high school cafeteria while the entire crowd was laughing. In the same time if one who

bullies other students at school is watching the movie alone may or may not identify himself with one of the bullies depicted in the movie. Because he is the bully and not the bullied; the issue is not important for him. There is a scene in the movie where the bullies, mainly the school's football team, and the bullied, Trevor, watch in the principal's office a video tape depicting cases of bullying which took place in the school on an everyday basis. All of them are confronted with the same story. Just after both parties are exposed together to the same reality which now they can share as spectators, some of the bullies understand the gravity of their acts and show remorse. Because of the drama he suffered, Trevor became bitter and tried to fabricate a tough image for himself, going so far as to make a false bomb threat on his high school. As an outcast his only support came from one of his teacher, Val Duncan (interpreted by Tom Cavanagh), who noticed that something happened with Trevor and tried to reach him. He does that by asking Trevor to take the main part in a play called *Bang Bang You're Dead*, depicting a teenager consumed by rage who is haunted by his parents and some school colleagues who he had shot dead. In this way Trevor is challenged to find his true self and to be saved from his anger and bitterness. On a personal note, I used this movie a couple of years ago while trying to solve a problem which occurred in my church youth group. A member of the group was always made fun of by the others. Any interventions from my behalf as a youth leader to straighten up this faulty behavioral attitude of some members of the group seemed to be failing. After watching the movie together with the entire group the problem was solved.

**A somewhat different approach:
the use of movies in ministering to troubled youth**

The movies which I used as examples share in a sense a common aspect depicted in different ways: suffering. This is a recurrent theme in many movies because it is one of the most common realities of life. C. Detweiler makes an interesting observation that explains the affinity for movies of today's generation in relation to suffering:

We turn to pop culture when we can't quite name our dilemmas. We may go to the movies as a way to buy time. It holds our demons at bay for a couple of hours. It offers some distance or perspective, a chance to worry about somebody else's quandaries. The best films and television series offer a vicarious experience where we can enter into the suffering of another and perhaps gain control or mastery over our own struggles. Surely Jesus offers the most vicarious example of taking on our suffering, entering in our world and our pain. Pop culture invites us to identify with a character. It is an opportunity to see ourselves in someone else's story.²⁸

In other words, movies become a means of reflection; a way of stepping back from our own suffering so that we could somehow understand it and better cope with it. They are a short refuge, a break from our sorrows, while contemplating someone else's problems. This should not be surprising. Suffering is often the means which drives the plot of a story. A brief explanation from literary theory may be useful at this point, an explanation from the way in which Aristotle viewed the link between plot and suffering. D. B. Morris explains: "Plot, for Aristotle is the soul of tragedy. While he insists that tragedies must include *pathos*, suffering alone does not create tragedy. It is the action, or plot, that creates a structure within which the *pathos* makes sense. Plot, then, for Aristotle, is what imparts to suffering its tragic status. . . . Plot, we might say, is somehow crucial to the generic framework within which both novels and tragedies place human suffering."²⁹ Suffering lays also at the heart of the Christian meta-narrative. Sin and suffering represent the plot of the human history, beginning with Adam and Eve. The coming of Christ into the world directly linked with the problem of sin and suffering. This is the reason why from all the actions present in a movie we probably best relate to suffering. In the words of D. B. Morris, "Suffering is an action. It is the outcome of a series of preceding acts. Indeed, this plot-centered view holds the promise of cognitive clarifications that may lead to the possibility of personal and social change. Although the protagonist of a tragedy or novel may be inextricably trapped within a structure of action too intricate or complex to reverse, the

reader or audience occupies a position in which the detachment... offers a crucial vantage point for securing knowledge and directing relief.”³⁰ Van Gelder’s observation shades even more light into the matter: “Needless to say, in a subjective image-driven, postmodern culture, the powerful character of film as a medium to present a more holistic version of reality tends to bias interpretation toward the viewer regardless of the intent of the director or author.”³¹ Or again, in Detweiler’s words: “Our pop culture habits reflect our passions, interests, and needs. Our favorite shows offer something we need—from surrogate friends and family to a laugh or a cry.”³²

Based on the observations that “postmodern culture... tends to bias interpretation towards the viewer,” that in pop culture “shows offer something we need,” and that through movies “we can enter into the suffering of another and perhaps gain control or mastery over our own struggles,” I dared to use movies in one on one ministering to troubled youth. The movie *Good Will Hunting*, released in 1997, starring Ben Affleck, Matt Damon, Stellan Skarsgård, Robin Williams, proved to be useful in this respect. Its use in youth ministry has been suggested by other authors.³³ I will make use of someone else’s summary³⁴ to remind about the movie:

For those unfamiliar with the film, *Good Will Hunting* is the story of a troubled young South Boston man who works as a janitor at MIT. A working class genius with a photographic memory who has mastered art, literature, history, and philosophy but whose special gift is mathematics, Will comes upon a problem a professor had left for his students to puzzle over and quickly but anonymously solves it. The professor, Gerald Lambeau, once a prodigy himself, discovers Will’s identity and takes him under his wing, rescues him from being sentenced to jail for barroom brawling, and makes him a member of his mathematical team. To deal with his antisocial behavior, the professor enlists as Will’s therapist a community college psychology instructor Sean McGuire (Played by Robin Williams), who is also the MIT professor’s Harvard roommate. The two vie for Will.³⁵

I thought the movie might be helpful in the counseling process (which is not totally unheard of)³⁶ of a troubled male teenager, member of the church youth group. I believed this could be possible because my expectations were that the teenager could easily draw some parallels between Will's story and his own. Like Will, he was raised without his parents who got divorced while he was very young. He was also a very intelligent young man, though his grades did not reflect that. He did not trust adults in a similar way in which Will (was diagnosed with reactive attachment disorder)³⁷ did not trust adults, so it was sometimes difficult for me to reach to him as it was for Sean McGuire, Will's therapist.³⁸ My hope was that the teenager could relate not just with Will's struggles, bitterness and pain, but also with Will's story positive outcome and with the hope which emerges at the end of the movie when all things seem to have worked out happily for Will. After viewing the movie, the teenager came quite relieved to the next pastoral counseling session (or probably a pedagogy session).³⁹ He admitted that he could identify himself with Will and his story (which, again, is not unheard of).⁴⁰

I do not to suggest that a movie could solve a teenager's problem or cure a person.⁴¹ But using the movie in ministering to a troubled teenager got me some time to figure out what should be done next in order to give him the best care I was able to give. Also the movie proved to be an encouragement for the teenager and helped him to overcome the depressive episode he was dealing with. After a couple of more meetings with the teenager I decided to send him to a professional Christian psychotherapist.

Though movies might have a multiple use in youth ministry, I find that movies can be used quite successfully in the area of ministering to troubled youth. A movie or a series can make a youth leader more aware of the problems the members of the church youth group might be facing, and more diligently look for signs of distress in the lives of teenagers. A movie can definitely be a break or a refuge from the bitter reality that teenagers may experience on a daily basis because of different life situations. But a movie can also offer encouragement and hope. In order to achieve this is very important to choose a movie with a positive ending and with heroes that manage to find their way through life.

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¹ Cf. Neil P. Hurley, *Theology Through Film*, New York: Harper & Row, 1970; Catherine M. Barsotti & Robert K. Johnston, *Finding God in the Movies: 33 Films of Real Faith*, Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Books, 2004; Anthony J. Klarke & Paul S. Fiddes, *Flickering Images: Theology and Film in Dialogue*, Oxford: Regents Park College, 2005; Clive Marsh, *Theology Goes to the Movies. An Introduction to Critical Christian Thinking*, Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge, 2007; Robert K. Johnson, *Reframing Theology and Film*, Grand Rapids, Michigan: Baker Publishing Group, 2007; Jeff Sellars, ed., *Light Shining in a Dark Place: Discovering Theology through Film*, Eugene, OR: Pickwick Publications, 2012.

² Cf. Jolyon Mitchell & Sophia Marriage, *Mediating Religion: Conversations in Media, Religion and Culture*, London/New York: T&T Clark Continuum, 2006; Melanie J. Wright, *Religion and Film: An Introduction*, London, New York: I. B. Tauris, 2007; John Lyden, ed., *The Routledge Companion to Religion and Film*, Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge, 2009; William L. Blizek, ed., *The Continuum Companion to Religion and Film*, London, New York: Continuum, 2009.

³ Cf. Doug Fields & Eddie James, *Videos That Teach* (Youth Specialties), Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1999; Doug Fields & Eddie James, *Videos That Teach 2* (Youth Specialties), Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2002; Doug Fields & Eddie James, *Videos That Teach 3* (Youth Specialties), Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2004; Doug Fields & Eddie James, *Videos That Teach 4* (Youth Specialties), Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2005; Bryan Belknap, *Group's Blockbuster Movie Illustrations*, Winona, MN: Saint Mary's Press, 2002; Bryan Belknap, *Group's Blockbuster Movie Illustrations: The Return*, Loveland, CO: Group Publishing, Inc., 2006; Bryan Belknap, *Group's Blockbuster Movie Illustrations: The Sequel*, Winona, MN: Saint Mary's Press, 2006; Eddie James & Tommy Woodard, *TV Shows That Teach: 100 TV moments to Get Teenagers Talking* (Youth Specialties), Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2008; Joel Mayward, *Jesus Goes to the Movies: The Youth Ministry Film Guide*, San Diego: The Youth Cartel 2015.

⁴ Cf. Craig Brian Larson & Andrew Zahn, *Movie-Based Illustrations for Preaching and Teaching: 101 Clips to Show or Tell*, Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2003; Craig Brian Larson & Lori Quicke, *More Movie-Based Illustrations for*

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⁵ Barsotti, Catherine M. and Robert K. Johnston, *Finding God in the Movies: 33 Films of Real Faith* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Books, 2004), 12.

⁶ A useful summary on the research done on these generations and on the different names given for each generation was produced by Eddy S. Ng & Emma Parry, "Multigenerational Research in Human Resource Management" in *Research in Personnel and Human Resources Management*, edited by M. Ronald Buckley, Jonathan R. B. Halbesleben, Anthony R. Wheeler, (Bingley, UK: Emerald, 2016), 1–10; 34.

⁷ An important research was done by Douglas Kellner, *Media Culture: Cultural studies, Identity and Politics between the Modern and the Postmodern*, London, New York: Routledge, 1995. Also see: Mark Gottdiener, *Postmodern Semiotics: Material Culture and the Forms of Postmodern Life*, Oxford: Wiley–Blackwell, 1995.

⁸ "As is well known, a culture is transmitted through various media but, more importantly, the media themselves transform culture. We then speak of a media-driven culture, or culture as spectacle, which at times takes the place of culture as such—an evolution that is rarely synonymous with enrichment or achievement in the Greek sense of the term." Joël Bonnemaison, edited by Chantal-Blanc-Pamard, Maud Lasseur & Christel Thibault, translated by Josée Pénot-Demetry, *Culture and Space: Conceiving a New Cultural Geography* (London, New York: I. B. Tauris, 2005), 69.

⁹ "We used to live in a word based print culture. We now live in a world where story and metaphor are at the heart of spirituality." John Roberto, *Becoming a Church of Lifelong Learners* (New London, CT: Twenty-Third Publications, 2006), 8.

¹⁰ Craig Van Gelder, "Reading Postmodern Culture through the Medium of Movies" in *Confident Witness—Changing World: rediscovering the Gospel in North America*, edited by Craig Van Gelder (Grand Rapids, MI / Cambridge, UK: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1999), 2, 39–66.

¹¹ It is important to note that postmodern culture was also described as *media driven* or *web driven*. See for example Ronald T. Michener, *Engaging Deconstructive Theology* (London, New York: Routledge, 2007), 5–6.

¹² "For young people accustomed to a participatory, image-driven culture, the power of outward signs—active tangible, and personal—is significant." Kenda Kreasy Dean, editor, *OMG: A Youth Ministry Handbook* (Nashville, TN: Abingdon Press, 2010), 75.

¹³ Robert K. Johnston, "Visual Christianity" in *The Conviction of Things Not Seen: Worship and Ministry in the 21st Century*, edited by Todd E. Johnson (Grand Rapids, MI: Brazos Press, 2002), 179.

¹⁴ This way of watching movies is supported by some school teachers that use movies as additional materials in their teaching. Rafe Esquith, *Teach Like Your*

Hair's On Fire: The Methods and madness Inside Room 56 (New York: Penguin Books, 2007), 89–92.

¹⁵ Theisen speaks about videos, referring to clips from movies. I am referring to the entire movies. Michael Theisen, *Youth Ministry Strategies: Creative Activities to Complement the Horizons Curriculum* (Horizons: A Senior Parish Religion Program; Winona, MN: Saint Mary's Press, 1998), E:48.

¹⁶ Theisen, E:48.

¹⁷ Theisen adds “in a church setting,” but this last observation seems unnecessary and may reflect a subjective thinking towards the relationship between sanctuary, worship, youth ministry and life outside church walls or church programs. Theisen also adds: “If the video you select is rated R, parents should be informed as to the reason for the rating and invited to attend the video viewing and discussion.” Theisen, E:48.

¹⁸ Theisen, E:48.

¹⁹ See Theisen, E:48–49.

²⁰ “It is critical that we stay informed about the types of entertainment that are having such an impact on the lives of young people. Not knowing about our kids’ movies, TV, or music [and I would add the internet and the social media] sends a message loud and clear: *We don't care!* If we are not informed, we communicate that we are not concerned about their lives.” Al Menconi, “Helping Youth Handle the Influence of Entertainment” in *Josh McDowell's Youth Ministry Handbook*, compiled by Sean McDowell & Ray Willey (Nashville, TN: Word Publishing, 2000).

²¹ In other words: “Build a reminder file to help you keep up with their favorite things—foods, music, books, places and movies.” Ginny Olson, Diane Elliot & Mike Work, *Youth Ministry Management Tools: Everything You Need to Successful Manage and Administrate Your Youth Ministry* (Youth Specialties; Grand Rapids, Michigan: Zondervan, 2001), 35.

²² Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru, “Modalități de educare a copiilor în familie (I)” in *Argeșul Ortodox*, X, No. 516, (Curtea de Argeș, Romania, 2011), 5.

²³ In other words: “In a typical *Judging Amy* episode Judge Amy Gray’s juvenile court case *and* her mother, Maxine’s social work case *and* the various family story lines are all tied up in the same set of thematic concerns, with interventions and variations running up against one another.” Michael Newman, “From Beats to Arcs: Towards a Poetics of Television Narrative,” in *Literary Theory: An Anthology*, edited by Julie Rivkin & Michael Ryan (Oxford: Wiley Blackwell, 2017), 256.

²⁴ Jeremy Halstead says: “My wife, Rhonda, includes girls when cooking and baking, shopping, scrap booking, crafting, and attending plays and movies.” Jeremy Halstead, *B. R. M. (Bathroom Reading Material) for Youth Workers* (Eugene, Oregon: Resource Publications, Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2014), 83.

²⁵ Lorenzo Carcaterra, *Sleepers*, New York, Toronto: Ballantine Books, 1995.

²⁶ Marilyn Kielbasa, *Total Youth Ministry: Ministry Resources for Pastoral Care* (Winona, MN: Saint Mary's Press, 2004), 147.

²⁷ A way of doing it would be: “Instead of having the young people come together to watch a movie and discuss it afterward, simply send out study guides for two to three movies per month and encourage young people to watch the movies and think about how the topics are covered.” Christina J. Semmel, *No Meeting Required: Strategies for Nongathered Ministry with Young People*, Winona, MN: Saint Mary’s Press, 2007.

²⁸ Craig Detweiler, “Screen Time: A Window into Teens’ Dreams” in *Adoptive Youth Ministry: Integrating Emerging Generations into the Family of Faith*, edited by Chap Clark (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2016), 71–72.

²⁹ David B. Morris, “About Suffering: Voice, Genre, and Moral Community” in *Social Suffering*, edited by Arthur Kleinman, Veena Das, & Margaret Lock (Berkeley & Los Angeles, CA: University of California Press, 1997), 37.

³⁰ Morris, 37.

³¹ Van Gelder, 53.

³² Detweiler, 71.

³³ It was suggested in relation to different topics (Action, Knowledge, Love, Obedience) and different Bible passages (Luke 6:46–49, James 1:22, 2:14–16). Fields, 1: 9, 11, 12, 16, 17.

³⁴ See also James J. Dowd, “Understanding Social Mobility Through the Movies” in *Cinematic Sociology: Social Life in Film*, edited by Jean–Anne Sutherland & Kathryn Feltey (Los Angeles, London, New Delhi, Singapore, Washington DC: Sage, 2013), 65–67.

³⁵ Jo Keroes, “Picturing Institutions: Intellectual Work as Gift and Commodity in *Good Will Hunting*” in *Imagining the Academy: Higher Education and Popular Culture*, edited by Susan Edgerton, Gunilla Holm, Toby Daspit, and Paul Farber (New York, London: RoutledgeFalmer, 2005), 42.

³⁶ “The power of cinema is especially in evidence when a patient in treatment reports feeling ‘cured’ by a film depicting psychotherapy. Some members of the audience identify so powerfully with the characters in the film that they may experience the therapy as if it were happening to them.” Glen O. Gabbard & Krin Gabbard, *Psychiatry and the Cinema* (Washington, DC / London: American Psychiatric Press, Inc., 1999), 181.

³⁷ “This condition was made popular by the movie *Good Will Hunting*. Children with reactive attachment disorder have learned that the world is unsafe, and have learned not to depend on adult caregivers. They develop a protective emotional ‘shell’, which isolates them from the pain of their attachment failure. These shells become very difficult to remove, as children depend on them as their sole means of coping with the world. Anyone who tries to remove this shell is seen as a threat and so they turn against the very people who want to help them the most, the caregivers.” Mike Cardwell & Cara Flanagan, *Psychology AS: The Complete Companion* (Cheltenham, UK: Nelson Thomas Ltd, 2005), 67.

³⁸ “Probably no film since *Ordinary People*, which appeared seventeen years earlier, has portrayed psychotherapy in such a positive light. Matt Damon portrays Will Hunting, a young man with impulse control problems who is ordered by the

court to see a therapist. He also happens to be a mathematical genius working as a janitor at MIT. A mathematics professor who recognizes his potential arranges for him to see a therapist played by Robin Williams. Much of the narrative hinges on the psychotherapeutic relationship between William's therapist and Damon's bad boy, who is far from a cooperative patient. Even though the movie suggests that psychotherapy is helpful, if not curative, for Will the treatment depicted is pure Hollywood fiction. In the first session, for example, when Will indirectly casts aspersions on his therapist's deceased wife, the therapist grabs him by the throat, pushes him against the wall, and threatens him." Gabbard, 144.

³⁹ An interesting observation: "In *Good Will Hunting*, therapy is a form of pedagogy, where the individual (Will, in this case), undergoes a reorientation of perspective." Penny Spirou, "O Captain, My Captain! Robin Williams and Transformative Learning in *Dead Poets Society*, *Good Will Hunting* and *Patch Adams*" in *Teaching and Learning on Screen: Mediated Pedagogies*, edited by Mark Readman (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2016), 36.

⁴⁰ There was the case of a twenty-three-year-old graduate student in humanities who went to psychotherapy for chronic feelings of depression identified himself with the character portrayed by Matt Damon. "After about three months of psychotherapy, the young man saw the film *Good Will Hunting*, and he came to his session the next day and asked his therapist if she had seen the film as well. She told him she had not. The patient then started crying and said through his tears, 'It was me.' The therapist asked him to elaborate. He clarified that just like Will Hunting, he had always blamed his abusive past on himself and he also said that the therapist played by Robin Williams reminded him a great deal of his mentor in graduate school. He said he was deeply moved when the therapist repeated over and over again, "It's not your fault, it's not your fault, it's not your fault." Gabbard, 181.

⁴¹ Regarding the twenty-three-year-old graduate student in humanities who went to psychotherapy is important to note that even though "he announced himself 'cured' by the movie of any deeply rooted issue," at the end "As one would expect, the 'cure' lasted only about a month and served as a resistance to more painful explorations of the past with all their ramifications in the patient's current life." Gabbard, 181-182.